

Agroforestry in France

Stakeholders Policy challenges

- Inventory of problems for each region and how was it solved
- Factsheets: current policy an AF at regional level
- The Bio-District: a new proposal for a strong cooperation to serve environment
- Fear of control, with a preference for no help to avoid deviating from specifications
- "Plenty of money to plant trees, but not enough to sustain them over the long term, which means that financial resources need to be earmarked. Poor publicity for failures due to inadequate support/lack of monitoring of plantations carried out "
- Unstable and restrictive public policies and CAP/Heterogeneous local policies (e.g. lack of coherence in the recovery plan)/ Fear of a reduction in UAA (CAP)
- Species that have been condemned (e.g. ash disease), with strict requirements for felling.

Policy recommendations

- 1.- Development of working groups to fit funds to existing challenges, reduce bureaucracy at minimum and adapt the legal framework for agroforestry practices implementation in both forest and agricultural land uses.
- 2.- Develop advisory systems linked to global and local research.
- 3.- Establish a short, intermediate and long term strategy to ensure agroforestry transition based on knowledge and digitalization.
- 4.- Understanding agroforestry as a land management ecosystem services provider and a value chain promotion linked to the use of the territory.
- 5.- Better understanding between the different ministries (i.e. environment and agriculture).

STATE:	France		Grassland	28,53%	37,72%
Nut level:	1		Agroforestry Practice Cover	2018	2022
Eurostat code:	FRD		Silvopasture	3,76%	5,32%
Area (km ²):	29.988		Agrisilviculture	0,00%	0,00%
Population	2018	2022	Agrosilvopasture	0,00%	0,00%
Population	3.327.477	3.339.074	Kitchen gardens	0,23%	0,25%
Density (p km ⁻²)	111	111	Holding type	2016	2023
Cover data	2018	2022	Natural person (ha)	-	511.140
Forest	18,78%	13,51%	Legal person (ha)	-	926.410
Arable land	40,19%	29,11%	Group holding and Common land unit (ha)	-	492.820
Permanent crops	0,06%	0,06%	Natural person (holder)	-	10.960
Agroforestry	3,99%	5,57%	Legal person (holder)	-	7.770
Shrubland	0,81%	2,18%			

Group holding and Common land unit (holder)	-	3.030
Regional Agricultural Area	Used	
	2016	2023
Farm number	-	21.770
Farm ha (UAA)	-	1.930.360
Animal populations (Thousand head)	2018	2023
Live bovine animals	2.149	1.964
Dairy cows	574	523
Non dairy cows	249	241
Live swine, domestic species	738	625
Live sheep	146	136
Live goats	7	12
CROPS (Hectares)	2016	2023
Utilised agricultural area	-	1.930.360
Cereals for the production of grain (including seed)	-	623.620
Common wheat and spelt	-	434.500
Durum wheat	-	-
Rye and winter cereal mixtures (maslin)	-	-
Barley	-	131.720
Oats and spring cereal mixtures	-	4.000
Grain maize and corn-cob-mix	-	42.580
Rice	-	-
Dry pulses and protein crops for the production of grain	-	20.270
Industrial crops	-	219.610
Cotton seed and fibre	-	-
Other oilseed crops n.e.c.	-	5
Fibre crops	-	77.320

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Aromatic, medicinal and culinary plants	-	35
Plants harvested green from arable land	-	337.260
Green maize	-	226.160
Kitchen gardens	-	10

Rural Development Interventions promoting agroforestry

ENVCLIM(70) - Environmental, climate-related and other management commitments

Interventions	9
Forestry	9
Crop diversification including woody perennials	3
Crop rotation including woody perennials	9
Livestock including woody perennials	0
Woody perennials to reduce soil erosion	3
Woody perennials to add organic matter	1
Woody perennials to reduce soil chemical contamination	3
Animal welfare using woody perennials	1
Permanent Grasslands with woody perennials	0
Agroforestry on Permanent Crops	2
Interventions	9

References

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- Population on 1 January by age, sex and NUTS 2 region (demo_r_d2jan) https://doi.org/10.2908/DEMO_R_D2JAN
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